

Effect of Physical and Nutritional Factors on the Growth and Sporulation of *Arthrinium phaeospermum* (Corda) M. B. Ellis.

I. B. Prasher, Radha Chauhan* and Aakash Singh

Mycology & Plant Pathology Laboratory, Department of Botany, Panjab University, Chandigarh- 160014 (India).

*Corresponding author: Radha Chauhan, Phone: +919876079956, E-mail: radhachauhann@gmail.com

Received: June 12, 2014; Accepted: July 17, 2014, Published: July 17, 2014.

ABSTRACT

Physiological studies pertaining to the effect of physical factors, carbon and nitrogen requirements of *Arthrinium phaeospermum* was conducted to know its behaviour *in vitro*. These studies have revealed interesting results regarding its growth and reproductive behaviour. The best medium for the optimum growth of the fungus is Glucose-peptone medium. The optimum temperature (28°C) and pH (8.0) is required for the optimum mycelial production of *Arthrinium phaeospermum* after 14 days of incubation. The best carbon source for the growth of the fungus is D (+) lactose whereas the fungus does not show any growth in L-sorbose medium. The best inorganic nitrogen source for the growth of the fungus is ammonium oxalate. The least mycelial growth of the fungus is observed in ammonium chloride and ammonium sulphate. The best organic nitrogen compound for the mycelial growth of fungus is L-proline. With L-tyrosine the fungus does not show any growth.

Keywords: *Arthrinium phaeospermum*, D (+) lactose, ammonium oxalate, L-proline.

INTRODUCTION

Physiological studies concerning growth and sporulation of *Arthrinium phaeospermum* with respect to different physical factors *viz*: temperature, pH and days of incubation and different carbon and nitrogen sources were conducted. *Arthrinium phaeospermum*; an anamorphic fungus which causes dermatomycosis in humans [1] and has been investigated previously for: possible production of growth promoting substances like organic acids [2,3], Hexylitraconic acid synthesis [2], its role as indoor air borne allergen organism [4,5,6], the production of metabolites [7], its antibacterial activity [8] and toxin production [9]; was selected. In spite of such a large number of physiological attributes of this fungus; which can be exploited commercially; no studies are reported till to date concerning the development of optimum basal medium for its growth and reproduction *in vitro*. The studies were therefore conducted to formulate an optimal basal medium for the growth and reproduction of this fungus for its commercial exploitation at a later stage and to conduct the studies concerning the control of dermatomycosis. This work pertains to the study of optimum physical (temperature, pH and days of incubation) and physiological requirements (carbon and nitrogen requirement) of *Arthrinium phaeospermum*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Microorganism:

The material of *Arthrinium phaeospermum* (Corda) M. B. Ellis was collected from the dead culms of *Bambusa* sp. from Bilaspur, Himachal Pradesh. It was isolated on Malt Extract Agar (Malt Extract 20g, Agar agar 20g, distilled water to make

1000ml) by single hyphal tip isolation at 24°C in petri-plates. For all experiments, the fungus was sub-cultured on the same medium. The stock cultures were kept at ±4°C in the refrigerator.

PROCEDURE

The effects of basal media, temperature, pH, days of incubation, carbon and nitrogen source on growth and reproduction of *A. phaeospermum* were observed in still cultures grown in 100 ml Erlenmeyer flask containing 25 ml of the basal medium (autoclaved at 15 psi pressure for 15-20 mins). Each flask was inoculated with an agar plug of 10 mm diameter cut from the margin of a 7-day old culture with a mycelial inoculum equivalent to 3.0 mg dry weight. Three replicates were kept for each parameter.

Determination of mycelial dry weight and final pH:

At the end of each experiment, the mycelia were harvested through pre-weighed Whatman filter paper No. 1 and dried at 45°C in a hot air oven and their dry weights were measured using an electronic balance (Sartorius Analytical BL 210S). The final pH of the culture filtrate of the individual replicate was checked over Digital pH Meter 813.

Basal Media:

The fungus was grown in twelve different media *viz*. Raulin's, Richard's, Dox's, Coon's, Brown's I, Brown's II, Glucose-peptone, Glucose-nitrate, Czapek's I, Czapek's II, Asthana & Hawker's and Elliot's medium.

Temperature:

In the experiment on the effect of temperature, the fungus was incubated at 16, 20, 24, 28 and 32°C, in basal medium

(Glucose-peptone) with a pH of 5 (selected arbitrarily) for 10 days of incubation.

H-ion concentrations:

In the experiment on the effect of pH, the pH levels of the medium were adjusted to 3.0-9.0 with a difference of unit pH. The pH of each aliquot was adjusted to a separate unit value aseptically with sterile 1N-HCl and 1N-KOH and checked over Digital pH Meter 813. The flasks were incubated for 10 days at 28°C.

Days of Incubation:

The effect of days of incubation on growth and reproduction of the fungus was studied for 20 days, at 28°C and at pH-8.0 (found optimum).

Carbon source:

The effect of the carbon sources (fructose, glucose, lactose, maltose, pectin, raffinose, sorbose, starch, sucrose and xylose) on *A. phaeospermum* mycelial biomass production and reproduction was evaluated at 28°C, pH-8.0 and after 14 days of incubation. The glucose of the glucose-peptone medium was substituted singly by each of the carbon compounds so as to provide 0.333g/l of carbon - a substituent of glucose (10g/l) in the basal medium.

Inorganic and organic nitrogen source:

The effect of different nitrogen sources was evaluated, replacing the peptone by different amino acids and inorganic nitrogen compounds (2.0 g/l) at optimum conditions i.e. at 28 °C and pH 8.0 in lactose supplemented basal medium for 14 days of incubation. Control without additional nitrogen source was run in parallel.

Incubation was carried out in 100 ml Erlenmeyer flasks with 25 ml of medium, which were inoculated with a 10 mm surface agar plug from 7 day old culture grown on MEA for all the experiments. Three replicates were maintained for each parameter for statistical studies. Cultures were filtered through Whatman filter paper No. 1 and dried overnight at 45-50 °C in a hot air oven. Dry weight of the mycelium was then determined using an electronic balance (Sartorius Analytical BL 210S).

Statistical analyses:

All the experiments were performed in triplicates. The means of three replicate values for all data in the experiments obtained were tested in a one way ANOVA at P=0.05 using PASW Statistics 18 software and Tukey’s test was used to evaluate differences between treatments.

RESULTS

Effect of Basal Media:

Glucose-peptone medium was the best medium for the optimum growth of the fungus (Fig. 1a). The fungus produced chlamydo spores in all basal media except Brown’s-II medium and it produced conidia in only Coon’s medium.

Effect of Temperature and pH:

The optimum temperature for the growth was 28°C whereas chlamydo spores were only formed at 24 and 28°C. The fungus did not show any growth at 32°C (Fig. 2a). The optimum H-ion concentration for the growth of the fungus was 8.0. It did not show any growth at pH 3.0 and 4.0 (Fig. 2b). The fungus reproduced by forming chlamydo spores at 24 and 28°C and pH 5.0-8.0.

Fig. 1a Growth (average mycelial dry wt.-mg/25ml) of *Arthrinium phaeospermum* with different basal media.

Effect of Days of incubation: The fungus attained maximum growth in terms of average mycelial dry weight (mg/25ml) on 14th day of incubation thereafter it decreased from 14-20 days (Fig. 3), whereas it reproduced by forming chlamydo spores after 6 days.

Fig. 2a Growth (average mycelial dry wt.- mg/25ml) of *Arthrinium phaeospermum* with different temperatures.

Fig. 2b Growth (average mycelial dry wt. mg/25ml) of *Arthrinium phaeospermum* with different H- ion concentrations.

Fig. 3 Growth (average mycelial dry wt. - mg/25ml) of *Arthrinium phaeospermum* with different days of incubation.

Effect of Carbon source:

The best carbon source for the growth of the fungus was found to be D (+) lactose whereas the fungus did not show any growth in L-sorbose medium (Fig. 4). The optimum production of biomass (average mycelial dry weight) in relation to the amount of sugar consumed (economic coefficient) in decreasing order is D (+) lactose> D (+) raffinose> pectin> D (+) xylose> D (-) fructose> starch> D (+) glucose> sucrose> maltose>. The fungus reproduced vegetatively by forming chlamydo spores in D (+) xylose, D (-) fructose, D (+) glucose, starch, maltose and D (+) raffinose supplemented basal medium. L (-) sorbose was found to inhibit the growth of the fungus whereas sucrose, lactose and pectin inhibited its sporulation.

Fig. 4 Growth (average mycelial dry wt. - mg/25ml) of *Arthrinium phaeospermum* with different carbon compounds.

Effect of Inorganic nitrogen source:

The best inorganic nitrogen source for the growth of the fungus was ammonium oxalate. The least mycelial growth of the fungus was observed in ammonium chloride and ammonium sulphate (Fig. 5a). The optimum production of biomass (average mycelial dry weight) in relation to the amount of sugar consumed (economic coefficient) in decreasing order was ammonium oxalate> ammonium phosphate> ammonium acetate> potassium nitrate> sodium nitrate> ammonium nitrate> ammonium chloride> ammonium sulphate. The fungus formed chlamydo spores in ammonium acetate, ammonium

chloride, ammonium nitrate, ammonium oxalate and ammonium sulphate whereas it reproduced asexually by conidial formation in ammonium acetate and ammonium oxalate.

Fig. 5a Growth (average mycelial dry wt. - mg/25ml) of *Arthrinium phaeospermum* with different inorganic nitrogenous compounds.

Effect of Organic nitrogen source:

The best organic nitrogen compound for the mycelial growth of fungus was L-proline (Fig. 5b). The optimum production of biomass (average mycelial dry weight) in relation to the amount of sugar consumed (economic coefficient) in decreasing order was L-proline> L-arginine HCl> L-cystine> L-asparagine> L-ornithine HCl> L-cysteine HCl> DL-valine> DL-tryptophan> L-glutamic acid> L-histidine HCl> L-leucine> DL-methionine> DL-aspartic acid> DL-threonine> glycine> L-α amino-n-butyrac acid> phenylalanine> DL-serine HCl> Lysine HCl. With L-tyrosine the fungus did not show any growth. The fungus formed chlamydo spores in all organic nitrogen compounds except in L-α-amino n-butyrac acid, L-cysteine HCl, L-cystine, glycine, DL-serine HCl and DL-valine whereas conidial formation occurred only in phenylalanine, L-proline and L-asparagine.

Fig. 5b Growth (average mycelial dry wt. - mg/25ml) of *Arthrinium phaeospermum* with different organic nitrogenous compounds.

DISCUSSION

The studies have revealed interesting results regarding its growth and reproductive behaviour. The best medium for the optimum growth of the fungus is Glucose-peptone medium. The optimum temperature (28°C) and pH (8.0) is required for the optimum mycelial production of *A. phaeospermum* after 14 days of incubation. High temperature (32°C) and highly acidic pH (pH 3 & 4) are found to be inhibitory for its growth. It has been found that composition of the basal medium, temperature and pH has significant effect on the reproduction of the fungus. It produces chlamydo spores in all basal media except Brown's-II medium; at 24 and 28°C; pH from 5.0-8.0. However, it produces conidia only in Coon's medium.

The fungus shows maximum biomass production with lactose which is in accordance with the previous reports on the stimulating effect of lactose on mycelial growth of *Alternaria citri*, *Alternaria tenuis* [10, 11], *Pestalotiopsis submerses* and *Flagellospora penicilloides* [12]. However, lactose was found to be a poor carbon source for mycelial growth of *Hirsutella rhossiliensis* [13], *Metarhizium anisopliae* [14], *Lentinus tuber-regium* [15], *Trichoderma viride*, *Beauveria bassiana* [16], *Tetracladium marchalianum* and *Tetrachaetum elegans* [12]. Pectin, D (+) raffinose, D (+) xylose, D (-) fructose, starch, D (+) glucose, sucrose and maltose supported good to moderate growth of the fungus. These results confirm the findings of Lilly & Barnett [17], Bilgrami & Verma [18]. Similar findings were observed in *Ustilago esculenta* [19], *Metarhizium anisopliae* [14], *Lentinus tuber-regium* [15], *Trichoderma viride* and *Beauveria bassiana* [16]. In showing nil growth with L (-) sorbose, it resembles fungi like *Cephalothecium roseum* [20] and *Nigrospora oryzae* [21], as it has been suggested to interfere with the respiratory pathways of the organism [22, 23]. Similar inhibitory effect of L-sorbose was found in *Helminthosporium turicum* and *Helminthosporium carbonum* [24], different strains of *Hirsutella rhossiliensis* [13]. The fungus reproduces vegetatively by forming chlamydo spores in D (+) xylose, D (-) fructose, D (+) glucose, starch, maltose and D (+) raffinose supplemented basal medium. L(-) sorbose is found to inhibit the growth of the fungus whereas sucrose, lactose and pectin inhibit its sporulation.

Studies on inorganic nitrogenous compounds reveal that the fungus gives maximum growth with ammonium oxalate followed by ammonium phosphate, ammonium acetate, potassium nitrate, sodium nitrate, ammonium nitrate and ammonium chloride. Similar stimulating effect of ammonium oxalate on growth has been observed in *Cercospora medicaginis* [25], *Cephalothecium roseum* [26] and *Helminthosporium setariae* [27]. However, these results are contrary to other findings where it supported poor growth of *Taphrina americana* and *Taphrina calrulescens* [28]. The fungus exhibited good to moderate growth with ammonium salts as have also been reported in other fungi e.g. *Gibberella zeae* [29], *Sclerotium cepivorum* [30], *Helminthosporium hawaiiense* [31] and *Ustilago esculenta* [19]. In utilizing nitrate sources of nitrogen *A. phaeospermum* resembles other fungi like *Metarhizium anisopliae* [14], *Curvularia lunata*, *Curvularia prasadii*, *Curvularia senegalensis*, *Curvularia clavata*, *Phoma vulgaris*, *Fusarium equiseti*, *Fusarium moniliforme*, *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Phoma nebulosa* and

Botryodiplodia theobromae [32], *Trichoderma viride* and *Beauveria bassiana* [16]. It gives poor growth with ammonium sulphate. Similar results were observed in case of *Curvularia lunata*, *Curvularia senegalensis*, *Curvularia clavata*, *Fusarium equiseti*, *Phoma nebulosa* and *Botryodiplodia theobromae* [32]. However, in *Curvularia prasadii*, *Fusarium moniliforme*, *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Phoma vulgaris* [32], *Trichoderma viride*, *Beauveria bassiana* [16], ammonium sulphate supported good to moderate growth. Sodium nitrite inhibit the growth of the fungus, as other reports suggested that it is non- available nitrogen source to several fungi like *Agaricus bisporus* [33], *Lentinus edodes* [34] and *Lentinula lateritia* [35].

Among organic nitrogen source, the fungus produced maximum biomass with L-proline followed by L-arginine HCl and L-asparagine to a fair extent. Similar findings have been reported in case of *Curvularia pallescens* [36], *Sclerotium cepivorum* [30], different strains of *Hirsutella rhossiliensis* [13], *Pestalotiopsis submerses*, *Flagellospora penicilloides* [12]. However, L-proline was reported as poor nitrogen source for growth of *Phellinus weirii* [38, 38], *Tetracladium marchalianum*, *Tetrachaetum elegans* [12]. L-tyrosine was found to inhibit the growth of this fungus which is contrary to other reports where moderate growth has been reported with L-tyrosine e.g. *Curvularia senegalensis*, *Curvularia clavata*, *Curvularia prasadii*, *Fusarium equiseti*, *Fusarium moniliforme* and *Phoma vulgaris* [32].

It produces chlamydo spores in basal medium containing ammonium acetate, ammonium chloride, ammonium nitrate, ammonium oxalate and ammonium sulphate as inorganic nitrogen compounds and in basal medium supplemented with DL-threonine, L-arginine HCl, DL-aspartic acid, L-histidine HCl, L-ornithine HCl, Phenylalanine, DL-methionine, DL-tryptophan, Lysine HCl, L-proline, L-leucine, L-glutamic acid and L-asparagine as organic nitrogen source.

The fungus reproduces asexually by forming conidia with ammonium acetate, ammonium oxalate (inorganic nitrogen) and phenylalanine, L-proline and L-asparagine as organic nitrogen source.

Acknowledgements

The authors are thankful to the Chairperson, Department of Botany, Panjab University for providing the necessary laboratory facilities and to UGC, (SAP, DRS-III) for the necessary equipment and infrastructural support.

REFERENCES

1. Y.M. Zhao, C.R. Deng, X. Chen, *Arthrinium phaeospermum* causing dermatomycosis, a new record of China, *Acta Mycologica Sinica*. 9 (1990) 232-235.
2. S. Tsukamoto, T. Yoshida, H. Hosono, T. Ohta, H. Yokosawa, Hexylitaconic acid: A new inhibitor of p53-HDM2 interaction isolated from a marine-derived fungus, *Arthrinium* sp., *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.* 16 (2006) 69-71.
3. S. Bloor, Arthrinic acid, a novel antifungal polyhydroxyacid from *Arthrinium phaeospermum*, *J. Antibiot.* 61 (2008) 515-517.
4. T. Takahashi, Airborne fungal colony-forming units in outdoor and indoor environments in Yokohama, Japan, *Mycopathologia* 139 (1997) 23-33.

5. O. Maggi, A.M. Persiani, F. Gallo, P. Valenti, G. Pasquariello, M.C. Sclocchi, M. Scorrano, Airborne fungal spores in dust present in archives: proposal for a detection method, new for archival materials, *Aerobiologia*. 16 (2000) 429-434.
6. H. Aydogdu, A. Asan, Airborne fungi in child day care centers in Edirne City, Turkey, *Environ Monit. Assess.* 147 (2008) 423-444.
7. E.K. Vijayakumar, K. Roy, S. Chatterjee, S.K. Deshmukh, B.N. Ganguli, H.W. Fehlhaber, H. Kogler, Arthrithitin. A new cell wall active metabolite from *Arthrimum phaeospermum*, *J. Org. Chem.* 61 (1996) 6591-6593.
8. L. Miao, T.F.N. Kwong, P.Y. Qian, Effect of culture conditions on mycelial growth, antibacterial activity, and metabolite profiles of the marine-derived fungus *Arthrimum c.f. saccharicola*, *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 72 (2006) 1063-1073.
9. S-J. Li, T-H. Zhu, Purification of the toxin protein PC from *Arthrimum phaeospermum* and its effect on the defence enzymes of *Bambusa pervariabilis* × *Dendrocalamopsis grandis* varieties, *For. Path.* 44 (2014) 96-106.
10. S.K. Hasija, Assimilation of sugars by *Curvularia pallescens*, *Alternaria citri* and *A. tenuis*, *Ind. Phyto. Path.* 21 (1968) 49-61.
11. S.K. Hasija, Physiological studies of *Curvularia pallescens*, *Nova Hedwigia*. 19 (1970) 551-558.
12. S. Bisht, Growth responses of aquatic hyphomycetes to different sources of carbon and nitrogen, *J. Appl. & Nat. Sci.* 5 (2013) 313-317.
13. X.Z. Liu, S.Y. Chen, Nutritional requirements of the nematophagous fungus *Hirsutella rhossiliensis*, *Biocontrol Science and Technology*. 12 (2002) 381-393.
14. T. Bharati, J.H. Kulkarni, P.U. Krishnaraj, A.R. Alagawadi, Effect of different carbon sources on the biomass of *Metarhizium anisopliae* (Ma2), *Karnataka J. Agric. Sci.* 20 (2007) 310-311.
15. J. Manjunathan, V. Kaviyaran, Physicochemical studies on *Lentinus tuberregium* (Fr.), A Indian edible fungus, *Int. J. Pharm. Pharm. Sci.* 3 (2011) 60-63.
16. J. Mehta, M. Jakheta, S. Choudhary, J. Mirza, D. Sharma, P. Khatri, P. Gupta, M.M. Nair, Impact of Carbon & Nitrogen Sources on the *Trichoderma viride* (Biofungicide) and *Beauveria bassiana* (entomopathogenic fungi), *Euro. J. Exp. Bio.* 2 (2012) 2061-2067.
17. V.G. Lilly, H.L. Barnett, *Physiology of Fungi*, McGraw-Hill Book Co. Inc., New York, Toronto and London, 1951.
18. K.S. Bilgrami, R.N. Verma, *Physiology of Fungi*, Vikas Publishing House Pvt. N. Delhi, 1978.
19. K.R. Chung, D.D. Tzeng, Nutritional requirements of the edible gall-producing fungus *Ustilago esculenta*, *J. Bio. Sci.* 4 (2004), 246-252.
20. K.S. Thind, M. Madan, Effect of various carbon sources on the growth and sporulation of *Cephalothecium roseum* Corda causing pink rot of apple (*Malus sylvestris* Mill.), *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.* 37B (1967) 273-280.
21. G.S. Rawla, S.K. Tandon, Nutritional requirements of fungi-I. Influence of different carbon compounds on the growth of *Nigrospora oryzae*, *Indian Journal of Mycology and Plant Pathology*. 7 (1977) 72-73.
22. V.G. Lilly, H.L. Barnett, The utilization of sugars by fungi, *Westva Uni. Agric. Expt. Sta. Bull.* 362T (1953) 5-58.
23. V.W. Cochrane, *Physiology of Fungi*, John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York, 1958.
24. I. Malca, A.J. Ullstrup, Effect of carbon and nitrogen on growth and sporulation of two species of *Helminthosporium*, *Bull. Torrey Bot. Cl.* 89 (1962) 240-249.
25. J.P. Goyal, P.N. Patel, Nutrition in relation to growth and sporulation of *Cercospora medicaginis*, *Ind. Phytopath.* 21 (1968) 241-248.
26. K.S. Thind, M. Madan, The effect of various nitrogenous sources on the growth and sporulation of *Cephalothecium roseum* Corda causing pink rot of apple (*Malus sylvestris* Mill.), *Ibid.* 39B (1969) 233-240.
27. P. Vidyasekaran, V. Mariappan, G.S. Smauel, C.V. Govindaswamy, Studies on physiology of *Helminthosporium setariae* the causal agent of leaf spot diseases of *Setaria italica*. I. Nitrogen nutrition, *Indian Phytopath.* 22 (1969) 480-488.
28. A.J. Mix, Differentiation of species of *Taphrina* in culture. Utilization of nitrogen compounds, *Mycologia*. 45 (1953) 649-670.
29. W.G. Bonn, R.A. Cappellini, Sporulation of *Gibberella zeae* III. Carbon and nitrogen nutrition on growth and macroconidium production, *Can. J. Bot.* 48 (1970) 1335-1337.
30. G.C. Papavizas, Carbon and nitrogen nutrition of *Sclerotium cepivorum*, *Mycol.* 62 (1970) 1195-1203.
31. S.M. Reddy, Nitrogen requirements of five species of *Helminthosporium*, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci. India.* 54 (1971) 142-146.
32. V.S. Dandge, Effect of nitrogen sources on the growth of different species of *Curvularia*, *Fusarium*, *Phoma* and *Botryodiplodia*, *Journal of Experimental Sciences.* 3 (2012) 24-27.
33. H.T. Hsu, K.J. Hu, Nitrogen nutrition of *Agaricus bisporus*. I Form of inorganic nitrogen utilized by *Agaricus bisporus*, *Nung Yen Chiu.* 16 (1967) 25-28.
34. K. Tokimoto, M. Komatsu, Biological nature of *Lentinus edodes*, in: S.T. Chang, W.A. Hayes, (Eds.) *The Biology and Cultivation of Edible Mushrooms*, Academic Press, New York, 1978.
35. T.G.B. Singh, R.N. Verma, Studies on carbon and nitrogen nutrition of *Lentinula lateritia* (Berk.) Pegler strains from North-eastern India, in: D. J. Royse, (Ed.) *Mushroom Biology and Mushroom Products*, Pennsylvania, U. S., 1996.
36. B.S. Bais, S.B. Singh, D.V. Singh, Effect of different carbon and nitrogen compounds on the growth and sporulation of *Curvularia pallescens*, *Ind. Phytopath.* 23 (1970) 511-517.
37. C.Y. Li, K.C. Lu, J.M. Trappe, W.B. Bollen, Selective nitrogen assimilation by *Poria weirii*, *Nature.* 213 (1967) 814.
38. C.Y. Li, W.B. Bollen, Growth of *Phellinus (Poria) weirii* on different vitamins and carbon and nitrogen sources, *Amer. J. Bot.* 62 (1975) 838-841.

Citation: Radha Chauhan et al (2014). Effect of Physical and Nutritional Factors on the Growth and Sporulation of *Arthrinium phaeospermum* (Corda) M. B. Ellis. J. of Advanced Botany and Zoology, VII4. DOI: 10.15297/JABZ.VII4.04.

Copyright: © 2014 Radha Chauhan. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.